

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2997168

: EDITORIAL

IEEE ACCESS SPECIAL SECTION EDITORIAL: ADDRESSING ECONOMIC, ENVIRONMENTAL, AND HUMANITARIAN CHALLENGES IN POLAR REGIONS

What is happening in the Polar Regions represents a meaningful and somehow amplified sample of the Global Climate Change (GCC) effects [item 1)–3) in the Appendix].

The deep transformation of Polar Regions will impact multiple activities and economic aspects related, for instance, to communications, transportation, oil exploration, fishing and even health of the polar and non-polar population. Some horizontal technologies, like remote and in-situ sensors, intelligent networks based on the integration among terrestrial, aerial and satellite nodes [item 4) and 5) in the Appendix], as well as data-driven transport systems, will be crucial to face the changes and counteract the related threats.

In 2017, IEEE Technical Activities started a visionary activity to identify the role IEEE could play in the planetary effort to counterbalance GCC at the Poles. In the frame of the activity, two events have been conceived and launched in order to create new opportunities for presenting ideas and results from the interested community: ASOF (Antarctic and Southern Ocean Forum) and ANOF (Arctic and Northern Ocean Forum), whose first editions have taken place in Australia (2018) and Finland (2019), respectively.

Some of the main actors that pioneered the 2017 activity also contributed to the development of this IEEE ACCESS Special Section, with the aim of expanding the opportunities of sharing ideas and results about Polar Region-related initiatives, findings and vision.

The Special Section is also conceived as a means in the publication area to increase sensitivity, to open new perspectives and to stimulate research and contributions to the key topic of the new challenges in Polar Regions within the IEEE-related scientific community.

Among the submitted articles, five contributions have been selected for the Special Section, where ideas and results that can benefit an effective polar-oriented research activity can be found. The polar efforts need cross/multi/trans-disciplinary teams, the ability of applying existing technologies to the specific needs of the polar challenge, as well as the capability of conceiving innovative technological, systemic and economic approaches to face and counteract the changes in Polar Regions.

The article, “GNSS Transpolar Earth Reflectometry exploriNg System (G-TERN): Mission concept,” by Cardellach *et al.*, presents a system that was proposed in response to an ESA call (Earth Explorer 9-revised) by a broad multi-disciplinary team composed of thirty-three scientists. The mission is primarily aimed at quantifying at high space-time resolution crucial characteristics, processes and interactions between sea ice and other Earth system components in order to improve understanding and prediction of GCC and its impact on both Environment and Society.

In the article “Design and optimization of a polar satellite mission to complement the Copernicus system,” by Alarcón *et al.*, the main results of the EU H2020 Operational Network of Individual Observation Nodes (ONION) Project, as well as the high-level design of the Marine Weather Forecast mission for Polar Regions, are presented. It is worth noticing that ONION has leveraged the concept of Fractionated and Federated Satellite Systems (FFSS) to develop and design innovative mission architectures resulting in a competitive advantage for European Earth Observation systems.

The article, “Benefits of using mobile ad-hoc network protocols in federated satellite systems for polar satellite missions,” by Ruiz-de-Azúa *et al.*, deals with satellite network routing protocols able to better cope with polar missions. In particular, considering the development of the mega-constellation concept, the applicability of the well-known Mobile Ad-Hoc Networks (MANET) architecture and the related Optimized Link-State Routing protocol to the satellite framework can be conceived, with benefits in terms of access time to polar satellite missions.

The article, “Enabling the Internet of Arctic Things with freely-drifting small-satellite swarms,” by Palma *et al.*, highlights that, despite the broad scientific and economic interests in the Arctic region, communications infrastructures are still scarce and costly. The authors show that freely-drifting small satellite swarms can enable the Internet of Things (IoT) in the most remote areas, including the Arctic, with an affordable cost-effective infrastructure.

Finally, the article, “Design and analysis of wireless sensor networks for animal tracking in large monitoring polar regions using phase-type distributions and single

sensor model,” by Vera-Amaro *et al.*, highlights that remote monitoring of animals in polar regions with traditional methods can be complicated and mostly inefficient. The article proposes the characterization of animal random trajectories by means of the random walk model in order to select the appropriate detection range and number of nodes to guarantee a target detection probability. Special attention is also provided to network simplicity and lifetime in terms of energy consumption.

As the Lead Editor, I hope that this Special Section will benefit the scientific community and contribute to the awareness of the old and new challenges in the Polar Regions. I would like to take this opportunity to applaud the contribution of the authors. The efforts of the reviewers to enhance the quality of the manuscripts are also truly appreciated.

I would like to express my deep appreciation and thanks to Adriano Camps, for his exceptional leadership of the group and the activities of “IEEE in the North and South Poles.” My sincere thanks also go to Paul Cunningham, William Emery, René Garello, Malcolm Heron, Witold Kinsner, and Tony Milne, who greatly contributed to the IEEE activities and new Events on the polar topic. Nothing would have happened without this group of pioneers, including this Special Section.

Finally, I would like to thank all readers: by spending your time in getting familiar with the content of the Special Section, you are already contributing to a topic that is crucial for the future of the Planet.

APPENDIX RELATED WORK

- 1) “Climate change-adapting to a changing arctic ocean,” *J. Ocean Technol., Fisheries Mar. Inst. Memorial Univ. Newfoundland*, vol. 11, no. 3, 2016.
- 2) *Goals and Objectives for Arctic Research 2017-2018*, U.S. Arctic Res. Program Plan.

MARINA RUGGIERI (Fellow, IEEE) is currently a Full Professor of telecommunications engineering with the University of Roma “Tor Vergata,” where she is also a member of the Board of Directors and the Co-Founder of CTIF, an interdisciplinary research center on information and communications technology and its verticals. She is an Arbitrator of the Italian Industries Federation for Aerospace, Defense and Security (AIAD), and a Principal Investigator of the 40/50 GHz Communications Experiment onboard Alphasat (launched on 2013). She is the author or coauthor of 350 articles, one patent, and 12 books. She is an Officer and a member of the Board of Governors of the IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Society (AESS), for the term of 2019–2021, the IEEE 2019 Technical Expert, and the IEEE 2017 Vice President for Technical Activities. She is a Fellow of IEEE “for contributions to millimeter-wave satellite communications.” She was a recipient of the 1990 Piero Fanti International Prize, the 2009 Pisa Donna Award, the 2013 Excellent Women in Roma Award, and the 2011 AESS Service Award. She has been inducted as a Professional into the IEEE Honor Society Eta Kappa Nu (HKN).

- 3) *Climate Science for Australia’s Future*, Antarctic Climate & Ecosyst. Cooperat. Res. Center, 2019.
- 4) E. Cianca, T. Rossi, M. Ruggieri, M. Presi, E. Ciaramella, L. Luini, C. Sacchi, G. Parca, and G. Codispoti, “Softwarization and virtualization as enablers for future EHF/FSO high throughput satellites,” in *Proc. IEEE Global Commun. Conf. (GLOBECOM)*, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates, Dec. 2018, pp. 1–6.
- 5) T. Rossi, M. De Sanctis, F. Maggio, M. Ruggieri, C. Hibberd, and C. Togni, “Smart gateway diversity optimization for EHF satellite networks,” *IEEE Trans. Aerosp. Electron. Syst.*, vol. 56, no. 1, pp. 130–141, Feb. 2020.

MARINA RUGGIERI, *Guest Editor*
University of Rome “Tor Vergata”
00133 Rome, Italy

WILLIAM J. EMERY, *Guest Editor*
University of Colorado Boulder
Boulder, CO 80309, USA

ADRIANO CAMPS, *Guest Editor*
Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya
08034 Barcelona, Spain

PAUL M. CUNNINGHAM, *Guest Editor*
IST-Africa Institute
Dublin, D03 Ireland

MAL HERON, *Guest Editor*
PortMapRemote Ocean Sensing
Townsville, QLD 4810, Australia

WITOLD KINSNER, *Guest Editor*
University of Manitoba
Winnipeg, MB R3T 2N2, Canada

ANTHONY MILNE, *Guest Editor*
School of Biological, Earth
and Environmental Sciences
University of New South Wales
Sydney, NSW 2052, Australia

WILLIAM J. EMERY (Fellow, IEEE) received the Ph.D. degree in physical oceanography from the University of Hawaii, Honolulu, HI, USA, in 1975.

He was with Texas A&M University, College Station, TX, USA. In 1978, he moved to The University of British Columbia, Vancouver, BC, Canada, where he created a Satellite Oceanography Facility/Education/Research Program. In 1987, he was appointed as a Professor of aerospace engineering sciences with the University of Colorado, Boulder, CO, USA. He is also an Adjunct Professor of informatics with the University of Rome “Tor Vergata,” Rome, Italy. He has authored more than 182 refereed publications, two textbooks, and more than 150 conference papers. He was an elected Fellow of the American Meteorological Society, in 2010, the American Astronautical Society, in 2011, and the American Geophysical Union, in 2012. He was a recipient of the 2004 IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Society (GRSS) Educational Award and the 2009 GRSS Outstanding Service Award. He was the Founding Editor of the IEEE GEOSCIENCE AND REMOTE SENSING LETTERS, in 2004, where he was the Editor-in-Chief for six years. He serves as the Editor-in-Chief for the *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*. He is the Vice President of Publications of the IEEE GRSS.

ADRIANO CAMPS was born in Barcelona, Spain, in 1969. In 1993, he joined the Electromagnetics and Photonics Engineering Group, Department of Signal Theory and Communications, UPC, as an Assistant Professor, where he was an Associate Professor in 1997, and has been a Full Professor since 2007. In 1999, he was on sabbatical leave at the Microwave Remote Sensing Laboratory, University of Massachusetts, Amherst. He has published over 203 articles in peer-reviewed journals, six book chapters, and the book *Introduction to Satellite Remote Sensing. Atmosphere, Ocean, Land and Cryosphere Applications* by Emery and Camps (Elsevier, 2017, 860 pages). He has more than 430 conference presentations, holds ten patents, and has advised 23 Ph.D. thesis students (more than nine on-going) and more than 140 final project and M.Eng. theses. According to Google Scholar/Scopus, his H-index is 46/37, and his publications have received more than 8919/6047 citations. His research interest includes microwave remote sensing, with special emphasis on microwave radiometry by aperture synthesis techniques (MIRAS instrument onboard ESA’s SMOS mission), remote sensing using signals of opportunity (GNSS-R), and nanosatellites as a tool to test innovative remote sensors.

PAUL M. CUNNINGHAM is currently the Director of the IST-Africa Institute; the President and CEO of IIMC, Ireland; an Adjunct/Visiting Professor with IUM, Namibia; and a Visiting Senior Fellow with Wrexham Glyndŵr University, U.K. He was the President of the IEEE SSIT from 2017 to 2018. He was the Chair of the IEEE Humanitarian Activities Committee in 2018, and serves on the IEEE Global Public Policy Committee.

MAL HERON (Fellow, IEEE) received the B.Sc. degree in physics, the M.Sc. degree (Hons.) in physics, and the Ph.D. degree in radio science from The University of Auckland. In 1971, he joined James Cook University, where he has served in several roles from teaching to research and administration. He is a retired Professor of physics with James Cook University, Australia. He is currently the CEO of PortMap Remote Ocean Sensing, research and consulting company. His research interests include radio wave propagation in the environment, physical oceanography, mesoscale meteorology, and physics of remote sensing. He is a Fellow of the Institution of Engineers Australia.

WITOLD KINSNER (Life Senior Member, IEEE) received the Ph.D. degree in electrical and computer engineering from McMaster University, Hamilton, ON, Canada, in 1974. He is currently a Professor with the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Manitoba, Winnipeg, Canada. He is a Fellow of the Engineering Institute of Canada, Engineers Canada, and the Canadian Academy of Engineering; a member of ACM; and a Professional Engineer with the Association of Professional Engineers and Geoscientists of the Province of Manitoba. Since 1971, he has been very active at all IEEE levels. He was the President of the IEEE Canada from 2016 to 2017, and the Director/Delegate of the IEEE Region 7 from 2016 to 2017. He was an elected IEEE Vice President of the Educational Activities Board in 2018, and re-elected in 2019.

ANTHONY MILNE was the Remote Sensing Science Manager of the Australian Government sponsored Cooperative Research Centre for Spatial Information from 2003 to 2010. He was the Co-Director of a private company, Horizon Geoscience Consulting Pty. Ltd., founded in 2002. He is currently a Visiting Professor of geography and remote sensing with the School of Biological, Earth and Environmental Sciences, University of New South Wales, Sydney, Australia. He has been a member of the IEEE GRSS AdCom since 2002. He currently leads the GRSS Globalisation Initiative. He has been a Principal Investigator in international research programs, including the NASA SIR-B and SIR-C radar missions, AIRSAR (USA), ERS-1 and ERS-2, ENVISAT(ESA), JERS-1, ALOS PALSAR (Japan), and MOMS (Germany). He was the Co-Chairman of three NASA AIRSAR Missions to Australia, South East Asia, and the Pacific, from 1994 to 2000 involving 18 countries. In his previous role as the Director of the Centre for Remote Sensing and GIS at the University of New South Wales, he was responsible for leading a team of multi-disciplinary researchers involved in environmental analysis. Recent research projects include Australian–Papua New Guinea radar topographic mapping and GEO-related forest and carbon assessment programs, and a series of projects for the NSW Government related to investigating the usefulness of radar to map flood patterns, vegetation condition, and the distribution of coastal and in-land riverine wetlands. His research interests include radar remote sensing, vegetation assessment, and the mapping of wetlands.

Dr. Milne is also a member of the Science Team for the Japanese Space Agency’s ALOS Kyoto and Carbon Initiative Research Program and has just retired as a Science Advisor to the Council of the International Society of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing. He was the Chair of the Membership Committee from 2004 to 2005, the Executive Vice President from 2006 to 2007, and the President of the IEEE GRSS from 2008 to 2009.

...